

EXPRESS ARTICLE

Edible, optically modulating, shape memory oleogel composites for sustainable soft robotics

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Shape memory oleogel composites
Optical modulation
Edible robotics
Sustainable robotics
Sensorized artificial muscle

ABSTRACT

The increasing impact of technology disposal and e-waste on the environment has driven robotics scientists to develop more sustainable robots. Biodegradable and edible shape-memory polymer artificial muscles represent an important robotic component that enables environmentally modulated deformation and movement. The need for finer behavioral control of artificial muscles also requires proprioceptive functionality. Here we report the first edible shape-memory oleogel composites that monolithically couple shape-memory actuation and color-change sensing within one material. The shape recovery and color change capabilities were characterized and two sustainable soft robots, a robotic gripper and a biomimetic flower, were constructed to demonstrate their potential for the development of sustainable and edible robotics.

The impact of technology disposal on the environment and the difficulty of recycling end-of-life appliances is driving the investigation into more sustainable alternative solutions [1], including the development of edible and sustainable soft robotics [2]. These new robotic technologies interact with nature and humans safely during their lifetime and, at the end of their productive life, degrade into nutritional materials to contribute to the next ecological cycle. They leave minimum footprints on the environment and can have a net positive impact. Artificial muscles (AMs) are a vital robotic component enabling controllable deformation and movement [3].

Shape-memory polymers (SMPs) represent an important category of AMs because of their ability to deliver large deformations. SMPs can recover from a temporary “programmed” shape to a “remembered” shape under a range of stimuli including heat, light, and magnetic and electrical fields [4]. Based on the number of programmable shapes the polymer can remember, SMPs can be classified into dual-, triple-, or multi-state SMPs. However, unlike biological muscle systems, SMPs often lack the proprioceptive capability that is required for better control and adaptation to a changing environment. When integrated into the AMs, previously developed sensing technologies, such as those based on resistance, capacitance, magnetics, and optics, can affect the intrinsic compliance of the muscle or require complex manufacturing [5]. Color-changing AMs represent a promising solution to proprioceptive

sensing as they can reflect the intrinsic artificial muscle state through color changes that can be detected remotely and wirelessly [6].

In this paper, we report the first edible shape-memory oleogel composites (SMOCs) with optical modulating capability, which monolithically integrate shape-memory actuation and proprioceptive color-change sensing within one material. Oleogels are structured oils formed by the addition of gelling agents and have been widely investigated to replace trans and saturated fats in foods for health purposes [7]. Ethylcellulose (EC) is recognized as the only direct edible polymer that can gel oils [8,9]. At the molecular level, ethylcellulose oleogels (ECOs) contain a 3D polymer network crosslinked via hydrogen bonding with the vegetable oils acting as the continuous phase (Fig. 1A) [8]. The hydrogen bonds act as netpoints to “remember” the permanent shape. In contrast to other shape-memory polymer composites that often explore “molecular switches” within the polymer chains as the shape fixation mechanism [10], our SMOCs use the thermally-triggered solid-liquid phase transition of coconut oil (CO) (Melting temperature: $T_{mco} = 24^\circ\text{C}$) to stabilize the temporary shape by immobilizing the polymer chains. When programming at elevated temperatures, the EC polymer chains and continuous phase are free to move and deform. However, upon cooling, the deformed shape is fixed via the crystallization of the CO phase, which is proposed to result in restriction of EC chain mobility.

ECOs were synthesized by pre-mixing EC (Sigma-Aldrich) at 30 wt% with CO (Sigma-Aldrich), then heating (200 °C) and stirring (200 rpm)

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Fig. 1. A. Illustration of the concept of the shape memory effect in oleogel composites. B. Bending recovery ratio over time at different temperatures (Material: EC 30 wt%). C. Optical modulation characterization (average temperature: 42 °C). D. Soft gripper demonstration. E. Biomimetic flower demonstration.

on a magnetic hotplate for 20 mins. To characterize the shape recovery, we performed bending recovery tests as below. The synthesized ECOs were first cast into a rectangular shape (10×60×3 mm), then bent to a specific angle ($\theta_0 = 160^\circ$ Fig. 1B Inset) under an elevated temperature (60 °C), cooled down while maintaining load (8 °C) for 1 min to fix the temporary shape and finally frozen (-19 °C) for 5 mins with load removed to further stabilize the deformation. To evaluate shape recover behavior, each ECO was placed in a water bath of specific temperature (20, 24, 40, 60, 80 °C). The change in bend angle (θ_t) was monitored closely using an overhead CCD camera for 10 mins. The shape recovery ratio (R_r) was calculated as $R_r = \frac{\theta_0 - \theta_t}{\theta_0} \times 100\%$ and plotted in Fig. 1B. See the supplementary video (SV) for more details. It is noted that SMOCs hold the temporary shape well when the temperature is lower than T_{mco} . SMOCs at 20 °C showed recovery that was hardly observable. Increasing the temperature not only enhanced the shape recovery but also increased the recovery speed. The recovery ratio increased from 10.2% at 24 °C to 90.3% at 80 °C, and the recovery saturation time decreased from 100 s at 60 °C to 35 s at 80 °C. Therefore, from these results we can see that the recovery ratio of these SMOCs are comparable to the SMPs reported in the literature [4].

In addition to the phase transition behavior, SMOCs also demonstrate optical modulation properties that could be used to monitor the shape recovery state and to proprioceptively determine the current state of the structure. The SMOC samples turned from an opaque state to a transparent state with increased temperature (Fig. 1C Inset). To show the potential for optical sensing, we quantified the change of color intensity over time while heating. The SMOC sample was placed above a blue background and under a CCD camera and a thermal camera, then heated using an air heater with both color and temperature continuously recorded. The normalized color intensity of a specific region of interest (ROI) (5 mm²) was calculated as $I = \frac{\text{Sum}\{I(x,y)\}}{255 \times R_x \times R_y} \times 100\%$, where $I(x,y)$ is the color density of pixel (x,y) and R_x and R_y are the x and y resolution (in pixels) of the image region being processed. As can be seen in Fig. 1C, the color intensity changed from 49.6% from the beginning to less than 30.4% at the end, with an average temperature of 42 °C. The plateau was due to the progressive heat transmission through the sample thickness (see SV).

To demonstrate the potential of our SMOCs in applications such as sustainable robots, we demonstrate a soft robotic gripper (Fig. 1D) and a biomimetic flower (Fig. 1E). The gripper (0.85g) was fabricated with

the SMOC in its closed shape and then programmed into the open shape at 60 °C, and fixed by cooling down to 8 °C. It was then held over a metal bolt (16.16g) and heated to stimulate shape recovery and closing of the gripper. It was demonstrated that the gripper could hold a weight at least 19 times its own weight even in its soft (warm) state. The biomimetic flower demonstrates an inverse actuation pattern to the gripper, namely from a programmed closed state to the as-fabricated open state. The edible SMOC was cast onto a thin layer of edible oil-based red dye, compressed to a thickness of 1 mm and finally die-cut into the flower shape as shown (Fig. 1E). It was then programmed to its closed state and put into a water bath (80 °C, a typical temperature for green tea). The flower demonstrated rapid blooming within 15 s, highlighting this material's potential to create simple edible biomimetic robots.

In this work, the first edible shape-memory oleogel composites that monolithically couples optical modulation and sensing with actuation are reported. This new class of material is promising for future sustainable soft robotics in medical applications such as edible satiation and drug release devices. More studies of shape memory, optical modulation properties long-term cyclic stability, transition temperature tuning, and edibility will be performed in the future.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data supporting this work is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5523/bris.grksw9h6gw1v2iyc5pwuqt9d>.

Acknowledgement

QQ, AK, and YK are supported by EU Horizon 2020 grant ROBO-FOOD (964596). JR is supported by EPSRC grants EP/L015293/1, EP/V062158/1, EP/S021795/1, EP/R02961X/1, EP/V026518/1, and EP/T020792/1, and the Royal Academy of Engineering through the Chair in Emerging Technologies scheme.

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112339>.

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